

UNIVERSITY OF DEUSTO

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

In Spain, gender-based violence (GBV) has been addressed institutionally by higher education institutions (HEIs) for over a decade, fundamentally as a result of the obligations created in this regard by various national laws, such as Organic Act No 3/2007 on Effective Equality between Women and Men, Act No. 14/2011 on Science, Technology and Innovation, and Law 1/2004 Comprehensive Protection Measures against Gender Violence. Although this act does not make specific detailed reference to universities, it does raise the issue of education and awareness and establishes that both the State and the Autonomous Communities, within the scope of their respective powers, will adapt their regulations to the provisions contained in the Law. As a result, all Autonomous Communities have adopted their own laws against GBV. Only the Law 17/2020 of the Autonomous Community of Catalonia mentions specifically GBV in Universities.

In the past five years, however, the treatment of GBV has been marked by a surge in awareness of its structural rather than individual nature and has therefore seen the further adoption and/or renewal of institutional policies aimed at addressing GBV in an integrated manner through measures of prevention, detection, investigation, prosecution, partnership, protection, and service provision.

The most common instruments used to address GBV in HEIs (prescribed by law) are Institutional Equality Plans, which increasingly include GBV among their other equality aims, and dedicated Protocols, which address one or more forms of GBV.

Over the past five years there has also been a proliferation of other types of action to address GBV at the institutional level in HEIs. Examples are the creation of specialised units, the integration of GBV into university curricula and research, the development of awareness-raising and training, the publication of statements, and the creation of protection mechanisms, services, and partnerships designed to promote an equal and non-violent environment and prevent and combat GBV in HEIs. In addition, GBV has been increasingly addressed by umbrella organisations such as the Network of Gender Equality Units (RUIGEU) and the Conference of Rectors (CRUE), which have issued statements to show their commitment to the elimination of GBV in HEIs. A defining feature of all these is that they have widened their subjective and material scope beyond the earlier focus on women and sexual and sex-based harassment. There is now a focus on other vulnerable groups, especially gender and sexual minorities, through the increasing adoption of an intersectional perspective, and on other forms of GBV, most notably online forms of GBV and sexual violence.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The University of Deusto (UD) has three main policy instruments to address GBV at the institutional level.

First, the Equality Plan 2020-2022, which addresses sexual and sex-based harassment along with other equality objectives. It focuses on prevention through awareness-raising and partnerships through the establishment of external partnerships to channel and address identified cases of GBV.

Second, the UD has two protocols dedicated to GBV, the Protocols for Prevention, Evaluation and Intervention in Situations of Harassment, one that applies to **staff** and one that applies to **students**. Their content, however, is the same and is referred to as 'the Protocol' in this vignette. Both address sexual, sex-based, moral or psychological, and discriminatory harassment and behaviour that, while not actually harassment, is considered inappropriate.

URLs

- › University of Deusto Equality Plan 2020-2022: https://www.deusto.es/cs/Satellite?blobcol=urldata&blobheader=application%2Fpdf&blobheadname1=Expires&blobheadname2=content-type&blobheadname3=MDT-Type&blobheadname4=Content-Disposition&blobheadvalue1=Thu%2C+10+Dec+2020+16%3A00%3A00+GMT&blobheadvalue2=application%2Fpdf&blobheadvalue3=abinary%3Bcharset%3DUTF-8&blobheadvalue4=inline%3Bfilename%3D%22EqualityPlan_English.pdf%22&blobkey=id&blobtable=MungoBlobs&blobwhere=1344509572680&ssbinary=true
- › Protocol for Prevention, Evaluation, and Intervention in Situations of Harassment in the Workplace at the University of Deusto: https://estudiantes.deusto.es/cs/Satellite?blobcol=urldata&blobheader=application%2Fpdf&blobheadname1=Expires&blobheadname2=content-type&blobheadname3=MDT-Type&blobheadname4=Content-Disposition&blobheadvalue1=Thu%2C+10+Dec+2020+16%3A00%3A00+GMT&blobheadvalue2=application%2Fpdf&blobheadvalue3=abinary%3Bcharset%3DUTF-8&blobheadvalue4=inline%3Bfilename%3D%22BOUD_64+Protocolo+de+Acoso+UD.pdf%22&blobkey=id&blobtable=MungoBlobs&blobwhere=1344444697233&ssbinary=true

Entry into force: The Protocol entered into force in 2017 and the UD Equality Plan in 2020.

TRAINING

The Equality Plan envisions among its prevention measures a plan of necessary training to identify and learn to respond to situations of sexual and gender-based harassment in order to ensure a safe environment, with the training actions aimed at specific audiences (students and administrative, research, and teaching staff).

The Protocol envisions the provision of training through seminars, conferences, and courses on prevention and on how to respond to cases of harassment, which will be offered every year in the

University Training Plan. Training programmes and training actions will be aimed at both UD staff, especially those with senior responsibilities at the administrative or academic level, tutoring staff, and those who provide direct care and psychological guidance services. In addition, the UD undertakes to provide the necessary specialised training and updates on psychosocial risks, harassment, and matters of equality and non-discrimination to the staff who are part of the Technical Commission on Harassment. The training programmes and actions on sexual harassment and discrimination provided as part of the university's training strategy will be carried out jointly with the Joint Equality Commission.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

The UD also organises other activities such as courses on sexual and gender-based harassment that are offered to new (teaching) staff, area managers, and members of the Technical Commission on Harassment, which combines teaching materials with face-to-face and online sessions. Of particular importance is the master's programme in Intervention in Violence Against Women offered by the UD, which trains professionals from various fields in how to intervene in cases of violence against women by providing them with the skills to design, plan, manage, execute, and evaluate care and initiate psychosocial, educational, socio-health, and / or legal interventions, based on a holistic vision of an intervention that considers the multiple factors that affect the needs and particular context of a woman in this situation. In 2018, this master's programme received an award from the Basque Women's Institute for its contribution to the qualified professionalization of the field of equality policies and intervention in violence against women. In addition, cooperation was established with Emakunde-Instituto Vasco de la Mujer, the Ertzaintza, and the Guardia Civil thanks to a research project on trafficking in women for the purpose of sexual exploitation, while associations which address gender based violence are involved in the master's programme mentioned above.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: Both the Equality Plan and the Protocols cover sexual harassment and gender harassment. In addition, the Protocols address psychological violence:

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: Together the policies cover all **7Ps** – prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, policy, and partnership. While the Equality Plan covers prevention and partnership, the Protocols cover all 7Ps except for partnerships.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Specific vulnerable groups

Not defined

Target groups

All the documents cover academic staff, non-academic staff, and students.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The Protocol refers to witnesses and any other person involved in the procedure in two measures of protection aimed mainly at victims: the adoption of precautionary measures during the procedure and the prohibition of retaliation.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The Protocol addresses the role of perpetrators in the complaint procedure.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Yes. The Equality Plan sets indicators relating to prevention and partnerships.

Prevention:

- (i) the number of training actions conducted, the number and position/responsibility of persons who have attended training, and the number of unit/department heads who have participated in training;
- (iii) the number of awareness-raising campaigns and campaigns on existing resources on violence against women developed; and
- (iv) the number of copies of the Protocol against harassment that are distributed and disseminated.

Partnership: (ii) the number and type of alliances created with external agents to address cases of GBV and the number of events carried out in collaboration with them.

Monitoring: Yes. The Protocol calls for the monitoring of the results of the institutional procedure.

The Protocol calls for the Technical Commission on Harassment to provide in its annual report information on situations of harassment and inappropriate behaviour that have been brought to its attention, while respecting the duty of confidentiality, and to include possible recommendations aimed at preventing situations of harassment. The UD undertakes to carry out studies to detect

and learn about harassment and to identify the factors and impact on the health of people and on the university organisation, in which the Health and Safety Committees, the Technical Harassment Commissions at the UD, the Own Prevention Service and the Joint Equality Commission participate.

Evaluation: Yes. The Equality Plan establishes evaluation as an axis of action but does not specify it further. The Protocol states that it will be subject to review every three years after it has come into force, and whenever requested by the Technical Harassment Commission regulated in the Protocol. It can also be requested by the Health and Safety Committees, the Prevention Service, or the Joint Commission on Equality, for which a joint review commission will be set up.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Yes. The Protocol sets out a step-by-step procedure for reporting and investigation for the case of violence among students, among staff and between staff and students.

The Protocol defines: Who to contact, how to report, the investigation procedure, timeframe, responsible persons, outcomes, sanctions.

The Protocol establishes a series of guiding principles for the procedure that are intended to help to protect victims, which include: applying maximum agility and speed, protecting and respecting the privacy and dignity of the people involved, taking into consideration the possible consequences, both physical and psychological, arising from this situation, and fully respecting the rights of the parties involved, especially their right to dignity and privacy. The procedure guarantees the rights of the claimant to physical and moral integrity and ensures that everyone involved, including those who provide testimony or information, as well as the people who make up the Technical Harassment Commission, are not subject to persecution, intimidation, discrimination, or retaliation, and this is to be achieved by adopting measures considered necessary and, where appropriate, demanding a disciplinary response. The procedure also allows for both parties to be accompanied by a person of their choosing during the procedure. For this purpose, they will be provided with a list of the people who make up the Health and Safety Committee and the Joint Equality Commission.

The Protocol stipulated that at any point in the procedure, from its start to its conclusion, as many precautionary measures may be taken as necessary to ensure the protection of the people involved. Such measures may include the relocation or separation of the parties in the given place of work or study, which includes their transfer to another job or place of study in order to avoid further harm. Such measures must not damage or substantially delay the working or academic conditions of any of the parties.

The procedure comprises three phases, the initiation phase, the investigation phase, and the resolution phase.

Who to contact, how to report, and the investigation procedure: The first phase begins with a letter in which the facts of the alleged harassment are communicated to the Technical Harassment Commission. The initial investigation actions are described, the precautionary measures that are to be taken are established, if applicable, and the decision on opening or filing a complaint is presented. The deadline for completing this initial phase may not exceed eight days from a complaint being reported. The Technical Commission on Harassment may carry out as many inquiries as it deems necessary regarding the facts that are the subject of the complaint. Then, within a maximum period of five days from the time when the first meeting was convened, it must

adopt a reasonable resolution, of which the parties must be notified, on whether to proceed to the investigation phase or to file a complaint.

The second phase includes instructional or research tasks. At the beginning of this phase, the person against whom a complaint has been made is informed of the facts that are the subject of the complaint and is asked to present the arguments in writing within seven days along with the evidence it deems appropriate. The Technical Commission on Harassment continues to gather the information and documentation necessary to obtain full knowledge of the facts and carry out as many tests as it deems necessary. The tests carried out are documented and once an examination of the facts and arguments made during the procedure has been carried out, the Technical Harassment Commission closes the second phase within a maximum period of 14 days from the start of the investigation.

Outcome, sanctions: In the third phase (resolution of the procedure) the Technical Harassment Commission is obliged to issue a report on its conclusions within a maximum of seven days of the conclusion of the investigation phase. The report on conclusions must contain: a) background information on the case, the complaint, and circumstances of the case; b) the facts that are considered proven; c) previous actions: the initial assessment of the case; d) a summary of the tests carried out; e) an assessment of the incident of harassment and its classification as a type of harassment; f) precautionary measures, if they have been agreed throughout the procedure; g) proposals for solutions and corrective / preventive measures to be implemented / executed by the university; h) additional recommendations, where appropriate; i) an indication of whether the decisions have been adopted unanimously or if there has been any disagreement. If the Commission rules that harassment has occurred, then the corrective, preventive, and disciplinary actions and measures that are considered appropriate will be adopted, and disciplinary proceedings will be initiated.

The steps for cases that include staff are exactly the same. The only difference is in the composition of the bodies that are in charge of the process, which in this case include representatives from trade unions.

Outcomes: Once the procedure is concluded, the Technical Harassment Commission proposes necessary measures to ensure that the conditions the victim experienced prior to the events reported are restored within the frame of organisational possibilities, without in any way causing harm to their previous employment situation and working conditions.

Sanctions: The Technical Commission on Harassment also proposes necessary measures to prohibit retaliation against people who have in one way or another participated in the investigation.

Responsible persons: In addition, the Protocol establishes that the Prevention Service is in charge of the custody of all the documentation and information produced in a case. This guarantees anonymity and prevents secondary victimisation.

This document reflects the situation as of April 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Lucrecia Rubio Grundell in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

